

No code, no problem - data analysis for biologists with Galaxy Australia

Dr Tiff Nelson and Dr Tristan Reynolds
Australian BioCommons

What is Galaxy Australia?

UseGalaxy.* members 2024

- Open-source web-accessible platform for data-intensive research.
- Global community
- Galaxy Project began in June 2005
- usegalaxy.org.au

What is Galaxy Australia?

Australian
BioCommons

*This service forms part of the national
Australian BioCommons infrastructure*

How is Galaxy Australia used in research?

Virus detection

Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus
(*Tobamovirus fructirugosum*) on
tomatoes and capsicum

- Agriculture outbreak threats, such as Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus (*Tobamovirus fructirugosum*).
- Serious economic damage with yield losses of up to 70%.
- Spread through trade of infected seed, plants, grafts and cuttings.

Image credit: agriculture.vic.gov.au/biosecurity/plant-diseases/vegetable-diseases/tomato-brown-rugose-fruit-virus

Virus detection

Image credit: agriculture.gov.au/about/news/look-inside-post-entry-quarantine-facility

- Detection undertaken in quarantine using wet lab methods, e.g. ELISA, PCR, microscopy.
- Low throughput.
- Associate Professor Roberto Barrero and colleagues developed bioinformatics toolkit.

Barrero et al. *BMC Bioinformatics* (2017) 18:26
DOI 10.1186/s12859-016-1428-4

BMC Bioinformatics

METHODOLOGY ARTICLE

Open Access

An internet-based bioinformatics toolkit for plant biosecurity diagnosis and surveillance of viruses and viroids

Roberto A. Barrero^{1*}, Kathryn R. Napier^{1,2†}, James Cunningham³, Lia Liefert⁴, Sandi Keenan⁵, Rebekah A. Frampton⁵, Tamas Szabo¹, Simon Bulman⁵, Adam Hunter¹, Lisa Ward⁴, Mark Whittam³ and Matthew I. Bellgard^{1*}

Article: doi.org/10.1186/s12859-016-1428-4

Virus detection

Article: <https://doi.org/10.3390/v14071480>

- Roadblocks in conversion to high throughput screening.
 - Requires computational resources.
 - Requires command-line environments (coding skills).
- GA-VirReport is a web-accessible version of the toolkit to virus screen during quarantine.

Virus detection

- GA-VirReport is now the **primary virus screening method** used for number of imported fruits and grasses.
- Over 4,000 jobs run per month since October 2022.
- Read recent news article at biocommons.org.au/news/daff-galaxy

Australian Government
Department of Agriculture,
Fisheries and Forestry

ABRicate tool

Klebsiella pneumoniae blaKPC gene for carbapenem-hydrolyzing class A beta-lactamase KPC-2, complete CDS

NCBI Reference Sequence: NG_049253.1

[GenBank](#) [FASTA](#)

Image credit: ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens/antimicrobial-resistance/

- ABRicate tool in high use for detection of known antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes.
- Allows mass screening of contig or GenBank files to identify these genes.
- Authored and created by bioinformatician, Associate Professor Torsten Seemann, The University of Melbourne
- More details - github.com/tseemann/abrigate

ABRicate tool

Veterinary Microbiology
Volume 248, September 2020, 108783

Genomic analysis of phylogenetic group B2 extraintestinal pathogenic *E. coli* causing infections in dogs in Australia

Amanda K. Kidsley ^{a, R, B}, Mark O'Dea ^b, Sugiyono Saputra ^{a, 2}, David Jordan ^c, James R. Johnson ^d, David M. Gordon ^e, Conny Turni ^f, Steven P. Djordjevic ^g, Sam Abraham ^{b, 1}, Darren J. Trott ^{a, 1}

Article: [10.1016/j.vetmic.2020.108783](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2020.108783)

[M]acromolecular Rapid Communications

Research Article | Open Access |

Anti-Pseudomonas Aeruginosa Bacteriophage Loaded Electrospun Fibers for Antibacterial Wound Dressings

Tian Ju, Jixuan Li, Andrew Weston, Giovanni Satta, Sara Bolognini, Mariagrazia Di Luca, Simon Gaisford, Gareth R. Williams

First published: 13 January 2025 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/marc.202400744> | Citations: 1

Article: doi.org/10.1002/marc.202400744

Galaxy
AUSTRALIA

SHORT CONTRIBUTION

Occurrence of *Salmonella enterica* in grey-headed flying foxes from New South Wales

F McDougall M Power

First published: 06 September 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.1111/avj.13116> | Citations: 1

Article: doi.org/10.1111/avj.13116

ENVIRONMENTAL MICROBIOLOGY

Research Article | Open Access |

Cyanobacteria as a critical reservoir of the environmental antimicrobial resistome

V. J. Timms, K. A. Hassan, L. A. Pearson, B. A. Neilan

First published: 26 June 2023 | <https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.16453>

Article: [10.1111/1462-2920.16453](https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.16453)

- Over 490,000 jobs run on Galaxy Australia have used ABRicate

ABRicate tool

Pathogen detection from (direct Nanopore) sequencing data using Galaxy - Foodborne Edition

Author(s) Paul Zierep

Editor(s) Wolfgang Maier

Reviewers

- Find ABRicate in a tutorial on Galaxy Training Network
- Read more about this tool here - biocommons.org.au/news/10m-jobs

Aiding ecology

Image credit: theguardian.com/

- Critically endangered swift parrot (*Lathamus discolor*).
- Breeds in Tasmania, winters in mainland Australia.
- Threats caused by habitat destruction (logging) and predation.
- Few hundred parrot individuals remain.

Aiding ecology

F1000Research

Publish fast. Openly. Without restrictions.

▶ F1000Res. 2024 Aug 27;13:251. Originally published 2024 Apr 4. [Version 2] doi:

[10.12688/f1000research.144352.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.144352.2)

▶ Other versions

A reference genome, mitochondrial genome and associated transcriptomes for the critically endangered swift parrot (*Lathamus discolor*)

[Luke W Silver](#)¹, [Dejan Stojanovic](#)², [Katherine A Farquharson](#)^{1,3}, [Lauren Alexander](#)^{1,3}, [Emma Peel](#)^{1,3}, [Katherine Belov](#)^{1,3}, [Carolyn J Hogg](#)^{1,3,a}

▶ [Author information](#) ▶ [Article notes](#) ▶ [Copyright and License information](#)

PMCID: PMC11411239 PMID: [39301273](#)

Article: f1000research.com/articles/13-251/v2

- Professor Carolyn Hogg, Dr Luke Silver and colleagues at University of Sydney assembled reference genome from PacBio HiFi reads.
- Genome 1.24 MB
- Completed Aves BUSCO - 97%
- Annotated transcriptome assisted annotation for critical understanding.

Aiding ecology

Australian BioCommons Community

Back to How-to Hub GitHub

About

Genome assembly ^

HiFi genome assembly on Galaxy Australia

Assess the quality of your genome assembly

Genome scaffolding with Hi-C on Galaxy Australia

Genome annotation v

Population genomics v

Genome-assembly

Genome assembly with `hifiasm` on Galaxy Australia

Galaxy Australia is capable of *de novo* assembling genomes based on PacBio high fidelity reads built from circular consensus sequence HiFi reads.

This How-to-Guide will describe the steps required to assemble your genome on the Galaxy Australia platform, using multiple workflows (see Fig 1) developed in consultations between the Bioplatforms Australia Threatened Species Initiative, Galaxy Australia, and the Australian BioCommons.

Note: If you need help, the Galaxy community is both approachable and helpful. Ask them questions!

- Followed 'hifiasm' workflow.
- australianbiocommons.github.io/how-to-guides/genome_assembly/hifi_assembly

How can I use Galaxy Australia?

Navigating Galaxy Australia

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with categories: Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, and Notifications. The 'Tools' section is expanded, showing sub-sections: FILE AND META TOOLS (Get Data, Send Data, Collection Operations), GENERAL TEXT TOOLS (Text Manipulation, Filter and Sort, Join, Subtract and Group), and GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION (FASTA/FASTQ, FASTQ Quality Control, SAM/BAM, BED, VCF/BCF, Nanopore, Convert Formats). The main content area features a top navigation bar with 'Home', 'News', 'People', 'About', 'Support', and 'Docs'. Below this is a large banner for the 'Galaxy AUSTRALIA platform 2024 update published!' with a link to 'Read the latest developments supporting accessible, reproducible, and collaborative data analyses' and a DOI: doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae410. A globe icon with 'usegalaxy.*' is also present. Below the banner, a paragraph states: 'Galaxy Australia is an open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research. Galaxy supports thousands of documented and maintained tools that are free to use. We facilitate on-demand training capacities and provision 600GB for Australian institutional (and 100GB for other) users.' On the right, a 'History' panel shows a list of datasets: 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' (346 MB, 19 hearts, 158 thumbs up, 152 thumbs down), '237: MultiQC-web.html', '236: MultiQC-stats' (a list with 3 tabular datasets), '219: FastQC-files-raw.txt' (a list with 8 txt datasets), '218: FastQC-files-web.html' (a list with 8 html datasets), '191: MultiQC-web.html', '190: MultiQC-stats' (a list with 3 tabular datasets), and '173: FastQC-files-raw.txt' (a list with 8 txt datasets).

- Web-accessible interface
- Access to 1000's of bioinformatic tools
- Just sign up to start using it
 - Register with institutional email to get 600 GB
- usegalaxy.org.au

Navigating Galaxy Australia

- Powerful compute backend.
- Combination of: high CPU, high memory, GPGPU and rapid I/O.
- Sourced from AARNet, NCI, Pawsey, Nectar Cloud and Microsoft Azure.
- Unmetered compute (use as much as you like)

Navigating Galaxy Australia

- 👁️ far right
- History can be used to manage analysis projects
- Have many histories as you like
- Share histories
- Save histories

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. On the left is a sidebar with navigation options: Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, and Notifications. The 'Tools' section is expanded, showing categories like FILE AND META TOOLS, GENERAL TEXT TOOLS, and GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION. The main content area features a blue header with a navigation menu (Home, News, People, About, Support, Docs) and a central banner for the 'Galaxy platform 2024 update published!'. On the right, a 'History' sidebar is highlighted with a red border, listing various analysis histories such as 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC', '237: MultiQC-web.html', '236: MultiQC-stats', '219: FastQC-files-raw.txt', '218: FastQC-files-web.html', '191: MultiQC-web.html', '190: MultiQC-stats', and '173: FastQC-files-raw.txt'. Each history entry includes a search icon, a share icon, and a trash icon.

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Navigating Galaxy Australia - Uploading Data

- 👁️ far left
- List of icons to help you navigate
- Most Important - Upload

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. On the left, a vertical navigation sidebar is highlighted with a red box, containing icons for Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, and Notifications. The main content area features a blue header with the Galaxy Australia logo and a navigation menu (Home, News, People, About, Support, Docs). A central banner announces the 'Galaxy platform 2024 update published!' with a link to read the latest developments. On the right, a 'History' panel shows a list of recent datasets, including 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' and several 'MultiQC' and 'FastQC' files.

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Navigating Galaxy Australia - Uploading Data

- Upload files
- Choose local files
- Drag local files from your hard drive
- Upload files individually

The screenshot displays the 'Upload from Disk or Web to Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' interface. At the top, there are tabs for 'Regular', 'Composite', 'Collection', and 'Rule-based'. Below these, a table lists two files: 'SRR28912963_2.fast' (363 b) and 'SRR28912966_1.fast' (353 b). Each file row includes a file icon, a search icon, a dropdown menu set to 'Auto-detect', a search icon, a dropdown menu set to 'unspecified (?)', a gear icon, a progress indicator showing '100%', and a checkmark. At the bottom of the interface, there are buttons for 'Choose local file' (circled in red), 'Choose remote files', 'Paste/Fetch data', 'Start', 'Pause', 'Reset', and 'Close'. Additionally, there are dropdown menus for 'Type (set all): Auto-detect' and 'Reference (set all): unspecified (?)'.

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Uploading Data

- Upload files as a collection - useful for downstream analysis

Upload from Disk or Web to **Kombucha ITS - Test for QC**

Regular Composite **Collection** Rule-based

	SRR28912963_2.fas	363 b	Auto-detect	Q	unspecified (?)	⚙️	100%	✓
	SRR28912966_1.fast	353 b	Auto-detect	Q	unspecified (?)	⚙️	100%	✓

Type (set all): Auto-detect Q Reference (set all): unspecified (?)

Choose local file Choose remote files Paste/Fetch data Start Pause Reset Close

Upload from E

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Uploading Data

- Collections are list of related data files
- Access easily for analysis steps

Create a list of selected datasets From history: **Kombucha ITS - Test for QC**

This interface allows you to build a new Galaxy list of datasets. A list is a type of Galaxy dataset collection that is a permanent, ordered list of datasets that can be passed to tools and... ▼

↶ Reset ⌵ 2 elements in list Select all

247: SRR28912966_1.fastq.gz (fastqsanger.gz)	✓ Added to collection	- Remove
246: SRR28912963_2.fastq.gz (fastqsanger.gz)	✓ Added to collection	- Remove

Hide original elements

Name:

Cancel Create list

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Uploading Data

- Upload files from remote destinations

Upload from Disk or Web to **Kombucha ITS - Test for QC**

Regular Composite Collection Rule-based

Drop files here

Upload from Disk or Web

Type (set all): Auto-detect Reference (set all): unspecified (?)

Choose local file **Choose remote files** Paste/Fetch data Start Pause Reset Close

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Uploading Data

- Upload files from remote destinations
- Limit transfer to local environment
- See the [Top Tips video on uploading data](#)

The screenshot shows a search bar at the top with the text "search" and a close button (X). Below the search bar is a table with two columns: "Label" and "Details". The table lists several data sources, with "Genome Ark" highlighted in a light blue row. At the bottom right of the table, there are two buttons: "Cancel" (with an X icon) and "Select" (with a checkmark icon).

Label	Details
Library Import Directory	Galaxy's library import directory
Griffith ownCloud	Import your files from ownCloud. Configure access in User -> Preferences -> Manage Information
Dropbox	Your Dropbox files. Configure your access token via User -> Preferences -> Manage Information <code>details-gxfiles://genomeark</code>
Genome Ark	Access to Genome Ark open data on AWS.
1000 Genomes	Access to the 1000 Genomes Project with human genetic variation, including SNPs, structural variants, and their haplotype context.
The Cancer Genome Atlas	Access to the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)
COVID-19 Data	A centralized repository of up-to-date and curated datasets on or related to the spread

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Finding Tools

- 👁️ left
- Tools can be searched and sorted in a number of ways

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. On the left, a vertical navigation menu is visible, with the 'Tools' section highlighted in red. The 'Tools' section contains a search bar with the text 'search tools' and a list of tool categories: FILE AND META TOOLS (Get Data, Send Data, Collection Operations), GENERAL TEXT TOOLS (Text Manipulation, Filter and Sort, Join, Subtract and Group), GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION (FASTA/FASTQ, FASTQ Quality Control, SAM/BAM, BED, VCF/BCF, Nanopore, Convert Formats), and a partially visible 'MULTIMEDIA' section. The main content area features a blue header with the Galaxy Australia logo and a navigation bar with links for Home, News, People, About, Support, and Docs. A central banner announces the 'Galaxy platform 2024 update published!' with a link to read the latest developments. On the right, a 'History' panel shows a list of recent datasets, including 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' and several 'MultiQC' and 'FastQC' files.

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Navigating Galaxy Australia - Finding Tools

- Change the search mechanism
- Use EDAM (data analysis and management ontology)

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes the Galaxy logo, the text "Australia", and a user profile for "tiff_nelson". The left sidebar contains navigation icons for Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, and Datasets. The "Tools" panel is highlighted with a red box and contains the following sections:

- Tools
- Full Tool Panel
- ...by Ontology
 - EDAM Operations
 - EDAM Topics
- ...for Activity
 - Proteomics
 - Microbiology
- Single Cell

Below the Tools panel, the "GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION" section lists tools such as FASTA/FASTQ, FASTQ Quality Control, SAM/BAM, and BED. The main content area features a navigation menu (Home, News, People, About, Support, Docs), the Galaxy AUSTRALIA logo, and a banner for the "Galaxy platform 2024 update published!". The right sidebar shows a "History" section with a search bar and a list of datasets:

- 247: SRR28912966_1.fastq.gz
- 246: SRR28912963_2.fastq.gz
- 237: MultiQC-web.html
- 236: MultiQC-stats
- 219: FastQC-files-raw.txt
- 218: FastQC-files-web.html

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Navigating Galaxy Australia - Finding Tools

- Change the search mechanism
- Use EDAM (data analysis and management ontology)
- EDAM operations

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes the 'Galaxy Australia' logo, user information 'tiff_nelson', and storage usage 'Using 3% of 600.0 GB'. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, Pages, and Notifications. The 'Tools' section is expanded, showing a search bar with 'search tools' and a dropdown menu of tool categories. The 'ANALYSIS' category is highlighted, and a tooltip for 'Data retrieval' explains its purpose: 'Evaluate a DNA sequence assembly, typically for purposes of quality control.' The main content area features a banner for the 'Galaxy Australia has been upgraded to rel...' and a 'Galaxy AUSTRALIA' logo. Below the logo is a 'Galaxy platform 2024 update published!' announcement. The right sidebar shows a 'History' section with a search bar and a list of datasets, including 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' and various 'FastQC' and 'MultiQC' files.

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Finding Tools

- Change the search mechanism
- Use EDAM (data analysis and management ontology)
- EDAM Topics

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes the Galaxy logo, the text "Australia", and a user profile "tiff_nelson". A sidebar on the left contains navigation options: Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, Pages, and Notifications. The main content area is titled "EDAM Topics" and features a search bar with "search tools" entered. Below the search bar, a list of topics is shown, categorized under "BIOLOGY" and "CHEMISTRY". The "BIOLOGY" category includes: Marine biology, Microbiology, Metagenomics, Transcriptomics, Molecular biology, Epigenetics, Microbial ecology, RNA splicing, Environmental science, Ecology, and Biodiversity. The "CHEMISTRY" category includes: Computational chemistry, Computational biology, Probes and primers, Sequence analysis, Sequence assembly, and Nucleic acid sites, features and... A central banner announces a "Galaxy Australia has been upgraded to rel..." and a "Galaxy platform 2024 update published!" message. Below this, a paragraph describes Galaxy Australia as an open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational research. A right-hand sidebar shows a "History" section with a search bar and a list of datasets, including "Kombucha ITS - Test for QC" and several "FastQC" and "MultiQC" files.

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Finding Tools

- Change the search mechanism
- Advanced tool search

Galaxy Australia

Using 3% of 600.0 GB | tiff_nelson

Advanced Tool Search

Filter by name: any name

Filter by section: any section

Filter by EDAM ontology: any EDAM ontology

Filter by id: any id

Filter by repository owner: any repository owner

Filter by help text: any help text

Search ?

Galaxy Australia has been upgraded to rel...

Home News People About Support Docs

Galaxy AUSTRALIA

Galaxy platform 2024 update published!

Read the latest developments supporting accessible, reproducible, and collaborative data analyses

With contributions from 130 authors representing 60 institutions
doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae410

usegalaxy™

Galaxy Australia is an **open, web-based** platform for accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research. Galaxy supports thousands of documented and maintained tools that are free to use. We facilitate on-demand training capacities and provision **600GB** for Australian institutional (and 100GB for other) users.

Request access to specialised tools
AlphaFold 2, FGENESH++

9000+ Tools & Datasets
Ready to install

History

search datasets

Kombucha ITS - Test for QC

526 MB | 12 | 163 | 152

- 247: SRR28912966_1.fastq.gz
- 246: SRR28912963_2.fastq.gz
- 237: MultiQC-web.html
- 236: MultiQC-stats
a list with 3 tabular datasets
- 219: FastQC-files-raw.txt
a list with 8 txt datasets
- 218: FastQC-files-web.html
a list with 8 html datasets
- 191: MultiQC-web.html
- 190: MultiQC-stats
a list with 3 tabular datasets
- 173: FastQC-files-raw.txt
a list with 8 txt datasets

Navigating Galaxy Australia - Finding Tools

- Advanced search to find lists of tools

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia interface. The top navigation bar includes the Galaxy logo, the text 'Australia', and a user profile 'tiff_nelson'. The left sidebar contains navigation icons for Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, Pages, and Notifications. The main content area is titled 'Advanced Tool Search' and features several filter fields: 'Filter by name:' (with 'trim' entered and circled in red), 'Filter by section:', 'Filter by EDAM ontology:', 'Filter by id:', 'Filter by repository owner:', and 'Filter by help text:'. A 'Search' button is located below these filters. The 'Search Results' section, outlined in red, shows 20 tools found for the filter. The first tool is 'Trim leading or trailing characters' (Galaxy Version 0.0.2), categorized under 'Text Manipulation'. The second is 'ivar trim Trim reads in aligned BAM' (Galaxy Version 1.4.4+galaxy0), categorized under 'iVar' with owner 'iuc'. The third is 'seqtk_trimfq trim FASTQ using the Phred algorithm' (Galaxy Version 1.4+galaxy0), categorized under 'FASTA/FASTQ' with owner 'iuc'. The fourth is 'Trim.seqs Trim sequences - primers, barcodes, quality' (Galaxy Version 1.39.5.0), categorized under 'Mother' with owner 'iuc'. The right sidebar shows a 'History' section with a search bar and a list of datasets, including 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' and several 'FastQC' and 'MultiQC' files.

Simplifying Galaxy Australia with Labs

Simplifying Galaxy Australia with Labs

genome.usegalaxy.org.au

The screenshot shows the Galaxy Australia Genome Lab interface. The top navigation bar includes the Galaxy logo, the text 'Australia - Genome Lab', and a user profile icon circled in red. The user profile dropdown menu is open, showing the user's name 'tiff_nelson' and a list of labs: Proteomics Lab, Single Cell Lab, and Microbiology Lab. The main content area features the 'GENOME LAB' logo and a welcome message. A 'Data import and preparation' section is visible, containing a list of frequently asked questions.

Tools

- FILE AND META TOOLS
 - Get Data
 - Send Data
 - Collection Operations
- GENERAL TEXT TOOLS
 - Text Manipulation
 - Filter and Sort
 - Join, Subtract and Group
- GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION
 - FASTA/FASTQ
 - FASTQ Quality Control
 - SAM/BAM
 - BED
 - VCF/BCF
 - Nanopore
 - Convert Formats
 - Lift-Over
- COMMON GENOMICS TOOLS
 - Operate on Genomic Intervals
 - MiModD
 - Fetch Alignments/Sequences
- GENOMICS ANALYSIS

GENOME LAB

Welcome to the Galaxy Australia Genome Lab. Get quick access to tools, workflows and tutorials for genome assembly and annotation.
[What is this page?](#)

Data import and preparation

Overview Tools Workflows

If you are new to galaxy, uploading your data is a good place to start!
Check out the Tools and Workflows tabs for different approaches to uploading data.

- How can I import my genomics data?
- How can I subsample my data?
- How can I import data from the BPA portal?
- Can I upload sensitive data?
- Is my data private?
- How can I increase my storage quota?
- Tutorial: Quality Control

History

- 247: SRR28912966_1.fastq.gz
- 246: SRR28912963_2.fastq.gz
- 237: MultiQC-web.html
- 236: MultiQC-stats
- 219: FastQC-files-raw.txt
- 218: FastQC-files-web.html
- 191: MultiQC-web.html
- 190: MultiQC-stats
- 173: FastQC-files-raw.txt
- 172: FastQC-files-web.html
- 41: jo_meta_Nextseq_ITS.txt

Accessing Specialised Tools

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes the Galaxy logo, the text "Australia", and a user profile for "tiff_nelson" with a storage indicator showing "Using 3% of 600.0 GB".

The left sidebar contains a "Tools" section with a search bar and a list of categories: FILE AND META TOOLS, GENERAL TEXT TOOLS, GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION, and others. The "GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION" category is currently selected.

The main content area features a banner for "REGISTER NOW!" with the URL <http://gxy.io/GTA2025>. Below this, a paragraph describes Galaxy Australia as an open, web-based platform. Three boxes offer "Request now" buttons for:

- Request access to specialised tools (AlphaFold 2, FGENESH++ and Cell Ranger)
- 9000+ Tools & Datasets Ready to install
- Additional storage Available on request** (highlighted with a red border)

The right sidebar shows a "History" section with a search bar and a list of datasets, including "Kombucha ITS - Test for QC" and several "MultiQC" and "FastQC" reports.

Accessing Specialised Tools

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes the 'Galaxy Australia' logo, a search bar, and user information (tiff_nelson). The left sidebar contains navigation options: Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, Notifications, and More. The main content area features a 'Tools' section with a search bar and a list of tool categories: FILE AND META TOOLS, GENERAL TEXT TOOLS, and GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION. A central banner promotes a registration event with the URL <http://gxy.io/GTA2025>. Below this, a text block describes Galaxy Australia as an open, web-based platform. Three 'Request now' buttons are visible, with the middle one (for 9000+ Tools & Datasets) highlighted with a red border. The right sidebar shows a 'History' section with a search bar and a list of datasets, including 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' and several 'MultiQC' and 'FastQC' files.

Accessing Specialised Tools

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia web interface. The top navigation bar includes the 'Galaxy Australia' logo, user information (tiff_nelson), and storage usage (Using 3% of 600.0 GB). The left sidebar contains navigation options: Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, and Notifications. The main content area is titled 'Tools' and features a search bar. Below the search bar, tool categories are listed: FILE AND META TOOLS (Get Data, Send Data, Collection Operations), GENERAL TEXT TOOLS (Text Manipulation, Filter and Sort, Join, Subtract and Group), and GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION (FASTA/FASTQ, FASTQ Quality Control, SAM/BAM, BED, VCF/BCF, Nanopore, Convert Formats, Lift-Over). A central banner promotes a registration event with the URL <http://gxy.io/GTA2025>. Below this, a text block describes Galaxy Australia as an open, web-based platform. Three cards offer services: 'Request access to specialised tools' (AlphaFold 2, FGENESH++ and Cell Ranger) with a 'Request now' button highlighted in red; '9000+ Tools & Datasets Ready to install' with a 'Request now' button; and 'Additional storage Available on request' with a 'Request now' button. A 'History' panel on the right shows a list of datasets, including 'Kombucha ITS - Test for QC' and various 'MultiQC' and 'FastQC' files.

Accessing Specialised Tools

The screenshot displays the Galaxy Australia interface. The top navigation bar includes the Galaxy logo, the text 'Australia', and a user profile 'tiff_nelson' with a storage indicator 'Using 3% of 600.0 GB'. The left sidebar contains a 'Tools' section with a search bar and categories: FILE AND META TOOLS, GENERAL TEXT TOOLS, and GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION. The main content area is titled 'Request access to' and features a grid of four tool cards, each with an 'Apply now' button. A red box highlights this grid. Below the grid, a red dotted line points to a list of datasets on the right, including '219: FastQC-files-raw.txt', '218: FastQC-files-web.html', '191: MultiQC-web.html', and '190: MultiQC-stats'.

Galaxy Australia

Tools

search tools

FILE AND META TOOLS

Get Data

Send Data

Collection Operations

GENERAL TEXT TOOLS

Text Manipulation

Filter and Sort

Join, Subtract and Group

GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION

FASTA/FASTQ

FASTQ Quality Control

SAM/BAM

BED

VCF/BCF

Nanopore

Convert Formats

Lift-Over

Home News P

Request access to

[Go to support menu](#)

Galaxy Australia users from Australian institutions. Access to these tools is restricted. Access will usually be granted automatically to users from Australian institutions.

Please [contact us](#) if you have any further questions.

Predict protein structures with AlphaFold 2

Apply now

Annotate genomes with FGENESH++

Apply now

Perform single cell RNA-seq analyses with Cell Ranger

Apply now

Analyse data-independent acquisition (DIA) proteomics data with DiaNN

Apply now

219: FastQC-files-raw.txt

a list with 8 txt datasets

218: FastQC-files-web.html

a list with 8 html datasets

191: MultiQC-web.html

190: MultiQC-stats

a list with 3 tabular datasets

How does Galaxy support reproducibility?

Pipelines/Workflows

- Support reproducible data analysis
- Streamline and automation
- Simple scripting, e.g.:
 - Bash
 - Python
 - R
- Script based pipeline/workflow systems, e.g.:
 - Nextflow
 - Snakemake

```

8
9 // Global default params, used in configs
10 params {
11
12 // Input options
13 input
14     = null
15
16 // References
17 genome
18     = null
19 splice_sites
20     = null
21 gtf_extra_attributes
22     = 'gene_name'
23 gtf_group_features
24     = 'gene_id'
25 skip_gtf_filter
26     = false
27 skip_gtf_transcript_filter
28     = false
29 featurecounts_feature_type
30     = 'exon'
31 featurecounts_group_type
32     = 'gene_biotype'
33 gencode
34     = false
35 save_reference
36     = false
37 igenomes_base
38     = 's3://ngi-igenomes/igenomes/'
39 igenomes_ignore
40     = false
41
42 // UMI handling
43 with_umi
44     = false
45 skip_umi_extract
46     = false
47 umitools_extract_method
48     = 'string'
49 umi_dedup_tool
50     = 'umitools'
51 umitools_grouping_method
52     = 'directional'
53 umitools_dedup_stats
54     = false
55 umitools_bc_pattern
56     = null
57 umitools_bc_pattern2
58     = null
59 umitools_umi_separator
60     = null
61 umi_discard_read
62     = null
63 save_umi_intermeds
64     = false
65
66 // Linting
67 skip_linting
68     = false
69 extra_fq_lint_args
70     = '--disable-validator P001'
71
72 // Trimming
73 trimmer
74     = null
75 min_trimmed_reads
76     = null
77 extra_trimgalore_args
78     = null
79 extra_fastp_args
80     = null
81 save_trimmed_reads
82     = null
83 skip_trimming
84     = false
85
86 // BBSplit
87 bbsplit
88     = null
89 save_bbsplit_fastq
90     = null
91 skip_bbsplit
92     = false
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94 }
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133 /*
134
135 RUN MAIN WORKFLOW
136
137 */
138
139 workflow {
140
141     main:
142     // SUBWORKFLOW: Run initialisation tasks
143     // PIPELINE INITIALISATION (
144     //     params.version,
145     //     params.validate_params,
146     //     params.monochrome_logs,
147     //     args,
148     //     params.outdir
149 )
150 // WORKFLOW: Run main workflow
151 NFCORE_RNASEQ ()
152 // SUBWORKFLOW: Run completion tasks
153 // PIPELINE COMPLETION (
154 //     params.email,
155 //     params.email_on_fail,
156 //     params.plaintext_email,
157 //     params.outdir,
158 //     params.monochrome_logs,
159 //     params.hook_url,
160 //     NFCORE_RNASEQ.out.multiqc_report,
161 //     NFCORE_RNASEQ.out.trin_status,
162 //     NFCORE_RNASEQ.out.map_status,
163 //     NFCORE_RNASEQ.out.strand_status
164 )
165 }
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```


STAGE
 1. Pre-processing
 2. Genome alignment & quantification
 3. Pseudo-alignment & quantification
 4. Post-processing
 5. Final QC

METHOD
 - Green: Aligner: STAR, Quantification: Salmon (default)
 - Blue: Aligner: STAR, Quantification: RSEM
 - Red: Aligner: HISAT2, Quantification: None
 - Purple: Pseudo-aligner: Salmon, Quantification: Salmon
 - Orange: Pseudo-aligner: Kallisto, Quantification: Kallisto

Galaxy Workflows

- Workflows logically connect a collection of Galaxy steps including:
 - Inputs
 - Tools
 - Workflows
- Links the outputs from one tool to the inputs of another tool

Workflow Preview

[Download](#) [Import](#) [Run](#)

About This Workflow

PacBio HiFi genome assembly using hifiasm v2.0 - Version 32

Author
johan

All published Workflows by johan

Creators
Gareth Price

Description
Assembly visualisation and quality control workflow for high fidelity reads built from circular consensus sequence (PacBio HiFi) data.

Tags
[fastq](#) [hifiasm](#) [HiFi](#) [genome_assembly](#)

License
GNU General Public License v3.0 or later

Last Updated
Monday Sep 19th 13:32:22 2022 GMT+10

Sharing
Use the following link to share preview of this workflow:
<https://usegalaxy.org.au/published/workflow?id=36604d6ab0dee988>
Manage sharing settings here.

The diagram illustrates a complex Galaxy workflow for PacBio HiFi genome assembly. It begins with a 'FASTQ input' step, followed by a 'HiFi Adapter Filter' step. The workflow then proceeds through several assembly stages: 'Initial assembly', 'Iterative assembly', and multiple 'Primary assembly' steps. Each assembly step is connected to various tools, including 'Graphical Fragment Assembly' and 'N50filter'. The final output is a 'Primary assembly' step. The workflow is visualized on a grid background with zoom controls at the bottom left.

Galaxy Workflows

- Reproducible data analysis
 - Perform the same analysis steps on different datasets
 - Saves tool parameters - can be updated for individual Workflow runs
 - Automates running of steps in the Workflow once all inputs are available
 - Can be shared and published

Workflow Preview

Download Import Run

About This Workflow

PacBio HiFi genome assembly using hifiasm v2.0 - Version 32

Author

johan

All published Workflows by johan

Creators

Gareth Price

Description

Assembly visualisation and quality control workflow for high fidelity reads built from circular consensus sequence (PacBio HiFi) data.

Tags

fastq hifiasm HiFi genome_assembly

License

GNU General Public License v3.0 or later

Last Updated

Monday Sep 19th 13:32:22 2022 GMT+10

Sharing

Use the following link to share preview of this workflow:
<https://usegalaxy.org.au/published/workflow?id=36604d6ab0dee988>
Manage sharing settings here.

Import Published Workflows

The image displays two overlapping screenshots of bioinformatics workflow management platforms. The background screenshot is from WorkflowHub, showing a search for workflows with filters for 'Any time' and 'Any time' updated. The foreground screenshot is from Dockstore, showing the 'The Galaxy Intergalactic Workflow Commission' organization page. This page lists two workflow collections: 'Variant Calling' with 9 workflows and 'Vertebrates Genome Project' with 13 workflows. The organization's goal is to improve workflow reproducibility through versioning, metadata capture, and help for finding workflows.

WorkflowHub Interface:

- Search: Search here... [Search]
- Workflows: 304 Workflows matching the given criteria: (Clear all filters)
- Workflow type: Galaxy
- Filters: Created At (Any time), Updated At (Any time), Tool (MultiQC, fastp, SAMtools, BUSCO, BWA, Minimap2)
- Workflow 1: gromacs-dctmd/main
Perform dcTMD free energy simulations and calculations
Type: Galaxy
Creators: Simon Bray, Simon Bray
Submitter: WorkflowHub Bot
Created: 7th Dec 2021 at 03:01, Last updated: 24th Apr 2025 at 03:01
- Workflow 2: tissue-microarray-analysis/main
Complete multiplex tissue image (MTI) analysis pipeline for tissue microarray (TMA) data: illumination correction, stitching and registration, and tissue microarray segmentation. T

Dockstore Interface:

- Organization: The Galaxy Intergalactic Workflow Commission
- Members: 9, Updates: 10
- Variant Calling: 9 Workflows [View]
- Vertebrates Genome Project: 13 Workflows [View]
- About the Organization: <https://github.com/galaxyproject/iwc>
- IWC - Intergalactic Workflow Commission
- Reproducibility is important. Our goals are to:
 - foster workflow use
 - incorporate versioning
 - capture more metadata: (names, versions, authors, use cases, etc.)
 - help scientists find workflows!

Extract Workflow from History

History + ⇌ ☰

You have 57 histories.

- Show Histories Side-by-Side
- Resume Paused Jobs
- Copy this History
- Delete this History
- Export Tool Citations
- Export History to File
- Archive History
- Extract Workflow**
- Show Invocations
- Share or Publish
- Set Permissions
- Make Private

Workflow name

Workflow constructed from history 'Galaxy Basics for everyone - Iris Species'

Create Workflow Check all Uncheck all

Tool	History items created
Data Fetch <i>This tool cannot be used in workflows</i>	1 iris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Treat as input dataset iris
Convert CSV to tabular <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Include "Convert CSV to tabular" in workflow	2 iris tabular
Remove beginning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Include "Remove beginning" in workflow	3 iris clean
Cut <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Include "Cut" in workflow	4 iris species column
Unique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Include "Unique" in workflow	5 iris species

Create Workflow

Galaxy Australia

Workflows

+ Create Import

My workflows Workflows shared with me Public workflows

Search my workflows by query or use the advanced filtering options

Sort by: Name Update time Filter: Show deleted Show bookmarked Display:

edited about 29 hours ago never run

Unnamed Workflow

Add Tags

Edit

Galaxy Australia

Genome Assembly

Genome Assembly of M

assembly microgala

Add Tags

Galaxy Australia

Using 35% of 600.0 GB treynolds

Unnamed Workflow (unsaved changes)

Tools

fastqc

FASTQ Quality Control

FastQC Read Quality reports

FASTA/FASTQ

FastQC An alternative, more performant implementation of FastQC for high throughput sequence quality control

Convert Formats

Tabular to FASTQ converter

Mothur

Make.fastq Convert fasta and quality to fastq

1: Input Dataset

output (input)

2: FastQC

- Raw read data from your current history
- Contaminant list
- Adapter list
- Submodule and Limit specifying file
 - html_file (html)
 - text_file (txt)

Workflow Attributes

The screenshot shows the 'Attributes' panel for a workflow. The 'Attributes' tab is selected in the left sidebar. The main panel displays the following information:

- Name:** RNA-Seq reads to counts demo
- Version:** 16: Feb 25th 2025, 16 steps
- Annotation:** This workflow takes input sequence reads, performs quality control checks and cleaning, maps the reads with HISAT2 and counts the number of reads that map to genes with featureCounts.
- License:** *Do not specify a license.*
- Creator:** Tristan Reynolds
- Tags:** maseq_wf

The 'Version' dropdown menu is open, showing a list of versions. The current version is 13: Jan 21st 2025, 16 steps. The list includes:

- 13: Jan 21st 2025, 16 steps
- 1: Jan 20th 2025, 18 steps
- 2: Jan 20th 2025, 18 steps
- 3: Jan 20th 2025, 18 steps
- 4: Jan 20th 2025, 18 steps
- 5: Jan 20th 2025, 18 steps
- 6: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- 7: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- 8: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- 9: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- 10: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- 11: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- 12: Jan 20th 2025, 16 steps
- ✓ 13: Jan 21st 2025, 16 steps

The text 'organization.' is written below the dropdown menu.

Using Subworkflows

The screenshot displays the Galaxy AUSTRALIA interface. On the left, a sidebar contains navigation options: Attributes, Inputs, Tools, Workflows (highlighted with a red box), Report, Best Practices, and Changes. The main workspace shows a workflow titled "RNA-Seq reads to counts de" with a search bar and a list of workflows. One workflow, "Filter Datasets", is highlighted. A red arrow points from this workflow to a detailed view of its steps, which include: 1. Input Dataset, 2. Count Chimeras in Files, 3. Create Table of File Names and Cluster Counts, 4. Select, 5. Add, 6. Add, 7. Add, 8. Add, 9. Add, 10. Add, 11. Add, 12. Add, 13. Add, 14. Add, 15. Add, 16. Add, 17. Add, 18. Add, 19. Add, 20. Add, 21. Add, 22. Add, 23. Add, 24. Add, 25. Add, 26. Add, 27. Add, 28. Add, 29. Add, 30. Add, 31. Add, 32. Add, 33. Add, 34. Add, 35. Add, 36. Add, 37. Add, 38. Add, 39. Add, 40. Add, 41. Add, 42. Add, 43. Add, 44. Add, 45. Add, 46. Add, 47. Add, 48. Add, 49. Add, 50. Add, 51. Add, 52. Add, 53. Add, 54. Add, 55. Add, 56. Add, 57. Add, 58. Add, 59. Add, 60. Add, 61. Add, 62. Add, 63. Add, 64. Add, 65. Add, 66. Add, 67. Add, 68. Add, 69. Add, 70. Add, 71. Add, 72. Add, 73. Add, 74. Add, 75. Add, 76. Add, 77. Add, 78. Add, 79. Add, 80. Add, 81. Add, 82. Add, 83. Add, 84. Add, 85. Add, 86. Add, 87. Add, 88. Add, 89. Add, 90. Add, 91. Add, 92. Add, 93. Add, 94. Add, 95. Add, 96. Add, 97. Add, 98. Add, 99. Add, 100. Add.

Below the workflow view, a subworkflow step is shown, titled "19: Filter Datasets". It has the following inputs: 0: Input dataset collection, 1: Input parameter, and two optional checkboxes: output_filtered (input) and output_discarded (input). A red arrow points from this subworkflow step back to the main workflow view, indicating its reuse.

- Reuse and insert an existing workflow as a single step inside of a new workflows.

Workflow Comments

- Assist Workflow readability
- Comment types
 - Text
 - Markdown
 - Frame
 - Freehand pen
- Tools within a frame are grouped
 - Moving the frame in the Workflow canvas moves all grouped tools
 - Can be used to group tools by analysis step

Workflow Invocations

Upload

Tools

Workflows

Workflow Invocations

Histories

History Multiview

Datasets

Libraries

Notifications

More

Workflow Invocations

Open Invocations List

- Assembly-Hifi-HiC-phasing-VGP4**
Using the VGP workflows to assemble a vertebrate genome with HiFi and H...
8 days ago scheduled
- kmer-profiling-hifi-VGP1**
Using the VGP workflows to assemble a vertebrate genome with HiFi and H...
8 days ago scheduled
- Mitogenome-Assembly-VGP0**
Assembly of the mitochondrial genome from PacBio HiFi reads
8 days ago scheduled
- Assembly-decontamination-VGP9**
Decontamination of a genome assembly
8 days ago scheduled
- Genome Assembly of MRSA using Illumina MiSeq Data**
Genome Assembly of a bacterial genome (MRSA) sequenced using...

Loaded 20 out of 107 invocations ↓

Sharing and Publishing Workflows

- Export and download as .ga files
 - Can upload to any Galaxy server (public or local)
- Share within Galaxy Australia
 - Share with specific users by email
 - Share as a link
 - Publish to make available to all users

Share or Publish Workflow "Filter Datasets"

- Make Workflow accessible
- Make Workflow publicly available in Published Workflows

This Workflow is currently accessible via link.

Anyone can view and import this Workflow by visiting the following URL:

url: <https://usegalaxy.org.au/u/treynolds/w/filter-datasets>

Share Workflow with Individual Users

You have not shared this Workflow with any users.

Please specify user email

Workflows

My workflows Workflows shared with me **Public workflows**

Search published workflows by query or use the advanced filtering options

Sort by: Name Display:

<p>edited 5 days ago <input type="button" value="Import"/> <input type="button" value="Play"/></p>	
<p>edited 5 days ago <input type="button" value="Import"/> <input type="button" value="Play"/></p>	

Sharing and Publishing Workflows

- Export and download as .ga files
 - Can upload to any Galaxy server (public or local)
- Share within Galaxy Australia
 - Share with specific users by email
 - Share as a link
 - Publish to make available to all users
- Embed Workflows on external websites
- Publish to workflowhub.eu and dockstore.org
 - Can import directly into Galaxy Australia

Embed code

```
<iframe title="Galaxy Workflow Embed" style="width: 100%; height: 700px; border: none;" src="https://usegalaxy.org.au/published/workflow?id: [ID]"></iframe>
```

Show embed Preview

What Galaxy Training and Support is Available?

The Galaxy Training Network (GTN)

Welcome to Galaxy Training!

Collection of tutorials developed and maintained by the worldwide Galaxy community

Galaxy for Scientists

We have separated the tutorials into several categories based on field and technology. We are exploring other ways to organise the tutorials going forward!

Start Here

Topic	Tutorials
Introduction to Galaxy Analyses	13
Using Galaxy and Managing your Data	22

Not sure where to start?

Try the NGS Basics Learning Path!

[Start Learning](#)

Scientific Fields

Topic	Tutorials
-------	-----------

Quickstart

Learning Pathways

Galaxy for Developers

Upcoming Events

Check out upcoming events around the

January 28, 2025
Galaxy at SURF Research Cloud v

Galaxy for SysAdmins

Topic	Tutorials
Assembly	19
Epigenetics	10
GMOD	14
Metabolomics	9
Proteomics	32
Sequence analysis	8
Single Cell	35
Synthetic Biology	3
Transcriptomics	24
Variant Analysis	17

Scientific Fields

Topic	Tutorials
Climate	12
Computational chemistry	9
SARS-CoV-2	9
Foundations of Data Science	49
Ecology	23
Evolution	9
FAIR Data, Workflows, and Research	23
Genome Annotation	20
Imaging	9
Materials Science	1
Microbiome	23
One Health	9
Plants	9
Statistics and machine learning	20
Visualisation	5

GTN Tutorial Resources

A short introduction to Galaxy

Author(s) Nicola Soranzo

Editor(s) Phil Reed

Reviewers

Overview

Questions:

- How to get started in Galaxy

Objectives:

- Learn how to upload a file
- Learn how to use a tool
- Learn how to view results
- Learn how to view histories
- Learn how to extract and run a workflow
- Learn how to share a history

Time estimation: 40 minutes

Level: Introductory

Supporting Materials:

 Available on these Galaxies

Published: Aug 27, 2018

Last modification: Mar 31, 2025

License: Tutorial Content is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#). The GTN Framework is licensed under [MIT](#)

PURL: <https://gxy.io/GTN:T0019>

Rating: 4.7 (104 recent ratings, 667 all time)

Revision: 43

Tutorial Recording - 18 March 2025

About this Recording

Speaker [Tristan Reynolds](#)

Captioneer [Tristan Reynolds](#)

Length 27 minutes

Created 18 March 2025

Archive [View tutorial at time of recording](#)

License [CC-BY](#)

Supporting Materials:

 [Slides](#)

 [Datasets](#)

 [Workflows](#)

 [FAQs](#)

 [Recordings](#)

 [Available on these Galaxies](#)

Galaxy Training Academy 2025

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One week of Free, Global, Online Galaxy Training

GTA
2025

WHEN?

From the 12th to 16th of May 2025

Learn about : Introduction to Galaxy, Assembly, Proteomics, Transcriptomics, Single Cell, Microbiome, Machine Learning, Python Intro, and much more!

<http://gxy.io/GTA2025>

Australian BioCommons Top Tips from Galaxy Australia

The screenshot shows the YouTube interface for the Australian BioCommons channel. On the left is a navigation sidebar with icons for Home, Shorts, Subscriptions, and You. The main content area features a featured video titled "A brief introduction to Galaxy Australia" by Dr. Gareth Price. Below this is a playlist titled "Galaxy Australia" by Australian BioCommons, which contains 11 videos and has 81 views. The playlist description states: "This playlist contains all videos that showcase the Galaxy Australia service. Visit the BioCommons website for more".

The video list on the right contains the following items:

- A brief introduction to Galaxy Australia**
Australian BioCommons • 197 views • 10 months ago
Duration: 4:08
- Top Tips from Galaxy Australia - Session 1**
Session 1: Saving time when uploading data
Australian BioCommons • 103 views • 7 months ago
Dr. Anna Syme
Duration: 13:48
- Top Tips from Galaxy Australia - Session 2**
Session 2: Choosing the right tool for the job
Australian BioCommons • 55 views • 7 months ago
Dr. Thomas Harrop
Duration: 16:31
- Top Tips from Galaxy Australia - Session 3**
Session 3: Staying organised
Australian BioCommons • 54 views • 6 months ago
Dr. Gareth Price
Duration: 25:02
- Top Tips from Galaxy Australia - Session 4**
Session 4: What to do when things go wrong
Australian BioCommons • 65 views • 6 months ago
Dr. Igor Mokunin
Duration: 15:02

Requesting Support

- Help desk - help@genome.edu.au
 - Support with errored jobs

7: Cutadapt on data 6: Read

1 Output

Add Tags

An error occurred with this dataset:
format **fasta**, database ?

```
-p out2.fa bsubtilis_ref_fasta_1.fa
bsubtilis_ref_fasta_2.fa
Processing paired-end reads on 5
```


Dataset Error Report

An error occurred while running the tool
toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/lparsons/cutadapt/cutadapt/4.9+galaxy1.

Details

Execution resulted in the following messages:

```
Fatal error: Exit code 1 ()
```

Tool generated the following standard error:

```
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/cutadapt/runners.py", line 105, in run
    for index, chunks in enumerate(self._read_chunks(*files)):
    ^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/cutadapt/runners.py", line 122, in _read_chunks
    for chunks in dnaio.read_paired_chunks(
    ^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/dnaio/chunks.py",
line 222, in read_paired_chunks
    raise ValueError(
ValueError: FASTA/FASTQ records do not fit into buffer of size
4000000

Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/cutadapt/runners.py", line 105, in run
    for index, chunks in enumerate(self._read_chunks(*files)):
    ^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^^
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/dnaio/chunks.py",
line 222, in read_paired_chunks
    raise ValueError(
ValueError: FASTA/FASTQ records do not fit into buffer of size
4000000
```

Requesting Support

- Help desk - help@genome.edu.au
 - Support with errored jobs
 - Request access to tools including
 - AlphaFold 2
 - FGENESH++
 - Cell Ranger
 - Request installation of new tools and datasets
 - Request additional storage

 Galaxy platform 2024 update published!

Read the latest developments supporting accessible, reproducible, and collaborative data analyses

With contributions from 130 authors representing 60 institutions
doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae410

Galaxy Australia is an **open, web-based** platform for accessible, reproducible and transparent computational research. Galaxy supports thousands of documented and maintained tools that are free to use. We facilitate on-demand training capacities and provision **600GB** for Australian institutional (and 100GB for other) users.

<p>Additional storage Available on request</p> <p>Request now</p>		
---	---	---

Galaxy Australia Training Infrastructure as a Service

Galaxy Australia - Training Infrastructure as a Service [🏠](#) [Calendar](#) [Stats](#) [Request](#)

Galaxy Australia is proud to provide Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS) for the Galaxy training community. You provide the training, we provide the infrastructure and cover all costs.

Why TlaaS?

All costs are covered by the Australian BioCommons for Australian users.

Priority job queue to service your training event effectively. See our [Event Dashboard](#).

No maintenance or administration required.

[Official Galaxy Training materials](#) are regularly tested and highly reliable.

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Melbourne Bioinformatics
BIOINFORMATICS • DATA SERVICES • INFRASTRUCTURE FOR LIFE SCIENCE TODAY

aarnet
Australia's Academic
and Research Network

Operational partners

Computational partners

Funding

